

Ibragimov Elshad Agaveli,
Doctor of Philosophy in Biology, Assistant
Department of Pediatric Dentistry
Huseynova Çeshmə Bahadır qızı,
Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant
Department of Orthopedic Dentistry
Gurskaya Narmina Azad
Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine Assistant
Department of Orthopedics Dentistry
Azerbaijan Medical University,
Baku, Azerbaijan
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ALGORITHMS FOR DIAGNOSTICS IN THE TREATMENT OF DENTAL CARIES IN CHILDREN

Abstract.

In modern pediatric therapeutic dentistry, the treatment of caries complications is one of the most challenging areas [3]. In this context, the quality of endodontic treatment plays a critical role, as it determines the positive prognosis for the long-term functionality of the tooth [2].

Keywords: diagnostics, endodontic treatment, complications of caries.

Errors in treating caries complications occur at all stages—from opening the tooth cavity to obturating the root canal system—and lead to serious complications in adjacent anatomical and topographical areas of the maxillofacial region [7]. Even with ideal filling of the root canal with sealing material, endodontic complications arise in at least 5% of cases. These complications are caused by root perforation, excessive extrusion of filling material, instrument breakage in the canal, and root apex resorption [5]. The overall frequency of such complications ranges from 15% to 60% [1], with molars accounting for 96% of cases [4]. Satisfactory filling of all root canals is achieved in only 5.4% to 13.4% of teeth [6]. Ineffective and low-quality initial endodontic treatment becomes the reason for tooth extraction in 6% of patients with chronic periodontitis [8].

Perforations of the hard tissues of teeth account for 3% to 12% of all complications in the therapeutic treatment of pulpitis and periodontitis. These often occur during the mechanical preparation of the tooth cavity and root canals. In the United States, up to 2,400,000 cases of endodontic perforations are recorded annually [9].

The emergence of a communication between the periodontal ligament and the tooth cavity leads to an inflammatory process at the perforation site and causes pathological changes in periodontal tissues. This occurs due to the loss of seal in the root canal system and bacterial invasion through the connection between the endodontic space and the oral cavity. In 85.3% of affected teeth, this results in resorption of bone and cementum, ultimately leading to tooth loss in the long term. Therefore, perforations should be considered a significant factor that limits the potential of endodontic treatment and significantly worsens its prognosis [11], although it should not be considered an absolute indication for tooth extraction in cases of caries complications.

However, in dentistry, tooth extractions are unjustifiably common in cases of hard tissue perforation [10, 12].

Thus, the high prevalence of caries complications among dental diseases, the often unsatisfactory outcomes of endodontic treatment due to low-quality perforation closure, the lack of clear guidelines for selecting methods to close perforations, and the challenges of rehabilitating patients with such pathology have formed the basis for further research.

The aim of the study is to improve endodontic treatment of caries complications in children by developing and implementing a diagnostic algorithm for selecting methods and materials to close perforations in the hard tissues of teeth.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in several sequential stages:

Identifying adverse outcomes of endodontic treatment and their causes based on the analysis of radiological data.

Investigating the topographical and etiological characteristics of root perforations in the hard tissues of teeth.

Conducting a retrospective analysis of cases involving re-endodontic treatment of teeth with hard tissue perforations and developing a prognostic criterion for evaluating the outcomes of endodontic treatment of such teeth.

Refining the classification of hard tissue perforations of teeth for clinical use and creating algorithms for selecting methods to close perforation openings in hard tissues, as well as for re-endodontic treatment of teeth with perforations.

Determining the clinical efficacy of endodontic treatment for teeth with root perforations using the proposed algorithms.

Study Materials

Imaging: Computerized tomography (CT) scans and intraoral targeted radiographs of 1,000 teeth were used to evaluate the quality of filling based on CT scans.

Teeth with Perforations: Teeth with hard tissue perforations were analyzed to study the localization and etiology of the perforations.

Medical Records: Medical charts of dental patients with records of root perforation treatment.

Diagnoses: Teeth diagnosed with K04.5 (62.7) periodontitis with hard tissue perforations were evaluated for treatment quality over both short- and long-term periods.

Chronic Apical Periodontitis: Teeth diagnosed with K04.5 (62.7) chronic apical periodontitis, complicated by root perforation, were treated according to developed algorithms, including perforation closure, and followed by regular check-ups.

Clinical Phase

The clinical phase involved 66 patients aged 10 to 18 years (39 girls and 27 boys) without significant systemic pathology. All patients were diagnosed with periodontitis (K04.5 (62.7)) and required re-endodontic treatment due to a defect in the hard tissues of the tooth in the form of a root perforation.

The selection criteria for teeth included in the study groups were standardized by diagnosis, the level and size of the perforation opening, and the size of the bone tissue destruction focus. This ensured comparability of the results obtained. A total of 72 teeth underwent re-endodontic treatment with perforation closure. The distribution of teeth with root perforations into study groups was based on the methods of treatment used.

Methods of Research

The study employed radiological, analytical, clinical, and statistical research methods. Perforations were classified using a "comprehensive clinical classification of hard tissue perforations," developed and adapted for clinical application and outcome prediction.

Evaluation of Treatment Quality

The quality of re-endodontic treatment was assessed at several stages:

Immediately After Treatment: The quality of perforation closure and root canal obturation was evaluated. Assessment criteria included the presence of radiopaque material matching the shape and size of the perforation and remaining within the contours of the tooth.

Short-Term Follow-Up: Clinical symptoms were monitored immediately after treatment and two weeks later.

Long-Term Follow-Up: Radiological examinations of treated teeth were conducted at 6, 12, and 18 months.

Results and Discussion

The findings indicate that high-quality endodontic treatment occurs in less than 42% of cases. The quality is notably lower in teeth with complex anatomy, such as the first molars of the maxilla and mandible (16.67%–32.82% of cases), compared to teeth with simpler anatomical structures, like the lateral incisors and first premolars of the mandible (73.33%–78.48%). The primary cause of unsuccessful endodontic treatment in 10.89% of cases was identified as perforations of the hard tissues of teeth (Table 2). This highlights the relevance of further research, given the high frequency of this complication and the inconsistent success rates in addressing it.

Timely diagnosis of perforations was lacking in 47.78% of cases. A significant number of cases involved apical resorption, necessitating re-endodontic treatment (46.84% of all perforations), as well as apical widening (19.30%). The high failure rate in endodontic treatment correlates with various types of perforations, emphasizing the insufficient exploration of methods and materials for resolving these defects.

More than 70% of root canal wall perforations occurred in the maxilla, whereas apical widening was more frequently observed in the first molars of the mandible (37%) and maxilla (20%). The results underscore the role of root canal curvature as a major etiological factor in perforations; 83% of perforations were associated with canal curvature. Most perforations occurred either before or at the curvature:

- Coronal third: 93% of cases
- Middle third: 85% of cases
- Apical third: 61% of perforations located distal to the curve

Perforation localization strongly correlated with the canal's direction and curvature angle. Common sites included canal bends with the following curvature angles:

- Medial bends: $>22^\circ$
- Distal and vestibular bends: $>26^\circ$ – 30°
- Oral bends: $>30^\circ$

These findings suggest that access challenges contribute to perforation occurrence. The majority (81%) of perforations occurred along the canal's outer curvature.

A predictive method for conservative treatment outcomes of teeth with root perforations was developed based on a retrospective study of re-endodontic treatment cases. This study included 86 clinical cases that met the data completeness criteria. Successful treatment outcomes were achieved in only 46.23% of perforation cases. Failure rates varied by perforation location, ranging from 38% to 69%.

- Resorptive perforations: 58.06% failure rate
- Iatrogenic perforations: 52.00% failure rate

Retrospective analysis revealed that clinical symptoms often persisted for extended periods after addressing furcal perforations and apical widening. Perforations in other locations tended to resolve more quickly, with symptoms subsiding immediately after treatment in 50% of cases.

Symptom Intensity and Perforation Size

The diameter of the perforation significantly influenced symptom resolution:

- Diameter <1 mm: Symptoms resolved immediately in 45% of cases.
- Diameter 1–2 mm: Symptoms resolved in 17.39% of cases.
- Diameter >2 mm: Discomfort resolved immediately in 66.67% of cases.

Bone tissue destruction sites recovered at varying rates depending on the perforation's location:

- Slower recovery for apical widening and middle-third canal wall perforations (6–12 months predominating).
- Full recovery observed within 6 months in 50%–57% of other locations.

Resorptive perforations required longer recovery periods (over 18 months) compared to iatrogenic perforations, which exhibited faster bone pattern restoration.

Development and Validation of a Diagnostic Algorithm

Based on extensive experience and research findings, a diagnostic algorithm for caries-related complications was developed and scientifically substantiated. Comparing the results of clinical and retrospective studies, it was established that the proposed algorithm improves the effectiveness of treating teeth with root perforations by 48.21%.

Higher treatment success rates were observed in the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th study groups compared to the retrospective analysis.

Conclusions

The anatomical and topographical features of the root canal system structure are among the etiological factors of perforation and determine their localization, size, and shape. At the same time, a number of etiological factors have been identified that most frequently contribute to the occurrence of perforations: the curvature of the root canal, the presence of a dentinal shoulder, root post, filling material, or a fragment of an instrument in the root canal, as well as obliteration of the root canal or pulp chamber. The identified features of the topography of hard tissue perforations of teeth, which are not included in existing classifications, must be considered when choosing the method and approach for their closure.

The use of the developed diagnostic algorithm increases the effectiveness of treating teeth with hard tissue perforations.

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